

Heaven's Light is Our Guide

Department of Computer Science & Engineering
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**Fake News Detection within a Static Dataset using
Supervised Machine Learning Algorithms**

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that this thesis report entitled “Fake News Detection within a Static Dataset using Supervised Machine Learning Algorithms” submitted by A. S. M. Shahadat Hossain, Roll: 123087 in partial fulfillment of the requirement for the award of the degree of Bachelor of Science in Computer Science & Engineering of Rajshahi University of Engineering & Technology, Bangladesh is a record of the candidate’s own work carried out by him under my supervision. This thesis has not been submitted for the award of any other degree.

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Abstract

In recent years, 'Fake News' has got an enormous sensation in our socioeconomic condition as well as in research community. It has become a very common and also a popular topic with respect to our day-to-day life. Fake news is a news created in an intent to spread misleading information or falsification. Number of fact checking or news verification systems is not increasing compared to the alarming increasing rate of fake news media. With the expansion of technological development, a real-time news verification suite has now become a demand of time. In fact, ability to detect deception within static datasets is to be ensured first to initiate developing a dynamic system for determining whether a news is authentic or deceptive. Machine Learning algorithms can play a vital role to automate the process of news verification. Supervised learning algorithms are those algorithms which learn from labeled data. This literature illustrates an implementation of fake news detection within a static dataset where few supervised learning algorithms like Support Vector Machine(SVM), Logistic Regression(LR) and Stochastic Gradient Descent(SGD) are used and among them, Logistic Regression (LR) provides the maximum accuracy of 92% for the dataset considered. It also introduces a novel general purpose model for fake news detection that combines both the linguistic approach shown and a network approach.

Contents

Acknowledgement	i
Certificate	ii
Abstract	iii
1 Introduction	1
1.1 Fake News & Its Types	2
1.2 Impact of Fake News	3
1.3 Supervised Machine Learning	3
1.4 Problem Formulation & Motivation	5
1.5 Objective	6
1.6 Organization	6
2 Related Work	7
2.1 Existing Solutions to Fake News Problem	8
2.1.1 FactCheck.org	8
2.1.2 B. S. Detector	9
2.2 Literature Review	10
3 Background Study	12
3.1 Support Vector Machine (SVM)	13
3.1.1 Working Principle of SVM	13
3.2 Logistic Regression (LR)	15
3.3 Stochastic Gradient Descent (SGD)	16
4 Methodology and Implementation	17
4.1 Methodology	18

4.2	Experimental Setup	19
4.3	Dataset Collection	19
4.4	Data Preprocessing	20
4.5	Feature Extraction	22
4.5.1	Bag of Words(BOW) model	22
4.5.2	<i>N</i> -gram Model	23
4.5.3	Bag of Words <i>N</i> -gram Model	23
4.5.4	TF - IDF Model	23
4.6	Applying Classifiers	24
5	Experimental Results & Analysis	25
5.1	Metrics to Measure Experimental Results	26
5.2	Experimental Results on Applying Models	27
5.2.1	Results Obtained by BOW <i>N</i> -gram Model	27
5.2.2	Comparison between BOW Unigram and Bigram Model	30
5.2.3	Results Obtained by TF-IDF <i>N</i> -gram Model	31
5.2.4	Comparison between TF-IDF Unigram and Bigram Model	33
5.3	Cross Validation	34
5.4	Summary of Experimental Result Analysis	36
6	Discussion and Conclusion	38
6.1	Summary	39
6.2	Limitations	39
6.3	Findings of this Research	40
6.4	Future Work	40
6.4.1	Proposed Fake News Model for Future Implementation	41

List of Figures

1.1	Types of Machine Learning (Adapted from [5])	4
1.2	Main Theme of Supervised Machine Learning [6])	4
3.1	Working Principle of SVM (Adapted from [20])	13
3.2	Sigmoid Activation Function	15
4.1	Block Diagram of the Methodology Followed	18
4.2	A News Article Before(left) and After(right) Data Preprocessing	21
5.1	Comparison of Classifiers' Performances for Unigram & Bigram Models	30
5.2	Comparison of Classifiers' Performances for Unigram & Bigram Models	33
5.3	Cross Validation for BOW Models	35
5.4	Cross Validation for BOW Models	36
6.1	Proposed Model for Fake News Detection	41

List of Tables

4.1	Brief Specification of the Dataset Used	20
4.2	Feature Extraction using BOW, Unigram Model	23
5.1	Confusion Matrix	26
5.2	Experimental Results on Using Unigram Model	28
5.3	Performances of Classifiers for BOW Unigram Model	28
5.4	Experimental Results on Using BOW Bigram Model	29
5.5	Performances of Classifiers for BOW Bigram Model	29
5.6	Performances of Classifiers for Unigram and Bigram Models	30
5.7	Experimental Results on Using TF-IDF Unigram Model	31
5.8	Performances of Classifiers for TF-IDF Unigram Model	31
5.9	Experimental Results on Using TF-IDF Bigram Model	32
5.10	Performances of Classifiers for TF-IDF Bigram Model	32
5.11	Performances of Classifiers for Unigram and Bigram Models	33
5.12	Cross Validation Accuracy for BOW Unigram and Bigram Models . . .	34
5.13	Cross Validation Accuracy for TF-IDF Unigram and Bigram Models . .	35

Chapter 1

Introduction

This chapter introduces the problem 'Fake News Detection' this literature focused on. Harmful effects caused by the problem are discussed here. Motivation behind choosing this problem as research topic is also included. Besides, this chapter lists the objective of the entire work. Moreover, concepts of Supervised Machine Learning are briefly described in this chapter. Finally, a section that provides the direction for readers to read the whole literature is added at the end of this chapter.

After all, this chapter includes the following topics:

- Fake News & Its Types
- Impact of Fake News
- Supervised Machine Learning
- Problem Formulation & Motivation
- Objective
- Organization

1.1 Fake News & Its Types

Fake news is a news which is created in an intent to spread falsehoods or misleading information. In other words, fake news is a type of yellow journalism or propaganda that consists of deliberate misinformation or hoaxes spread via broadcast news media or online social media [1]. Sometimes, it is also defined as “Fake news is an inaccurate, sometimes sensationalistic report that is created to gain attention, mislead, deceive or damage a reputation. Unlike misinformation, which is inaccurate because a reporter has confused facts, fake news is created with the intent to manipulate someone or something” [2]. They are often associated with eye-catching headlines containing sensational messages and fabricated deceptions. There are various types of fake news such as biased, rumor, conspiracy and so on. At the same time, a fake news can be spread in varieties of ways.

Fake news can be classified into numerous types. Besides, a fake news can also be classified from different perspectives; however, Rubin et al. [3] defined three types of fake news in their research work:

1. **Serious Fabrications:** Mainly kinds of news sometimes Tabloids emphasize such as sensational crime stories, astrology, gossip columns about celebrities, and junk food news. This type of news are usually unverified and often associated with headlines those are attractive. Besides, this types of news are sometimes created and spread to increase traffic of a particular site.
2. **Large-Scale Hoaxes:** This is another type of deliberate fabrication or falsification in the mainstream or social media. These are relatively complex and large scale fabrications.
3. **Humorous Fakes:** This type of fake news can also be called as satirical news where readers are aware of the humorous intent. Sometimes these news mimic credible news source and often achieve wide distribution.

There are also few other types of fake news such as ‘**Clickbait**’, ‘**Conspiracy**’, ‘**Bias**’, ‘**Pseudoscience**’, ‘**Propaganda**’, ‘**Misinformation**’ and so on.

1.2 Impact of Fake News

Impact of fake news is very dangerous for society as well as the whole world. There are many examples of that. Very few among them are as follows:

- According to an online news portal, in final phase of the American presidential election 2016, the 20 most successful false declarations were frequently shared, liked, and commented as the 20 most successful reports of serious media. [4]
- Early this year at Malaysia, an elderly Chinese woman was falsely accused of being part of a syndicate which kidnaps children. [4]
- During the general election in 2013, the ruling party of Malaysia was accused of importing 40,000 foreign workers from Bangladesh to be voters which created a lot of chaos at that time. [4]

These are only a very few of the enormous impacts of fake news problem. Although these news behind the above incidents were fake, their consequences were way bigger than of real news.

1.3 Supervised Machine Learning

Machine Learning is a field of computer science that gives computers the ability to learn without being explicitly programmed. It provides machines the ability to learn automatically and improve from experience. Besides, Machine Learning has a very close relationship with computational statistics, which focuses on prediction-making through the use of computers. Besides, it can also be seen as an application of Artificial Intelligence(AI).

Among different types of Machine Learning, Supervised machine learning is able to apply what has been learned in the past to new data using labeled examples predicting future events. Starting from the analysis of a known training dataset, the learning algorithm produces an inferred function to make predictions about the output values. The system is able to provide targets for any new input after sufficient training. The learning algorithm can also compare its output with the correct, intended output and find errors in order to modify the model accordingly.

Figure 1.1: Types of Machine Learning (Adapted from [5])

Figure 1.1 shows different types of Machine Learning where Supervised learning can be divided into few categories such as Regression, Classification and Ranking. Applying classification algorithms is one of the concerns of this literature. Other two types of supervised machine learning are beyond the scope.

Figure 1.2: Main Theme of Supervised Machine Learning [6]

Figure 1.2 represents working principle of Supervised Machine Learning. Among classification algorithms, Support Vector Machine (SVM), Logistic Regression (LR), Stochastic Gradient Descent (SGD) were used during this work. These algorithms were chosen by observing their successful performances in case of some important text classification problems like spam detection, sentiment analysis and so on. Details working principles of these algorithms are discussed briefly in Chapter 3 (Background Study).

1.4 Problem Formulation & Motivation

While surfing in a Bengali online news portal, the idea of working against fake news problem crossed the author's mind. Due to the existence of vast fabricated fake news in some news portal, decision was made to explore this problem and find a sustainable solution. The idea was instantly originated after observing some Bengali news portals; however, decision was made that the solution against the fake news written in English texts needs to be made first. Because, it can be believed that finding dataset to do experiment is at least less difficult for English texts compared to Bengali or any another language.

It is very difficult for public to be able to identify fake news or to know how to verify it or boycott those who spread it. Regardless of a few existing solutions like FactCheck.org [7] and B.S. Detector [8], there is neither any reliable system to verify a news whether it is authentic nor any reliable proposed method to mitigate the fake news problem considerably. Hence, it is a crying need to develop a news verification system.

It was felt that to reach at a solution to this problem, it is needed first to decide properly whether a news is real or fake. This thought made the foundation of all the motivations behind choosing the problem 'Fake News Detection' to work on. Besides, it should be confirmed first that we can detect fake news at least within static datasets. The model used in this detection within a static dataset can be employed to work in dynamic environment to fight against real time fake news. Moreover, a successful model for fake news detection can lead towards building a real time news verification suite.

Based upon the consequences, it is clear that the necessity of a news verification suite can not be denied by any means. In fact, this work is highly motivated to find a way to spot fake news. First of all, a Machine Learning based text classification is imposed to draw boundary between real and fake news. Empirical experiences show that considering Linguistic approach only is not sufficient for an ill posed problem like fake news detection. Since performances of different classification algorithms vary from dataset to dataset, interest of this literature also includes introducing a General Purpose Fake News Model.

1.5 Objective

Both the harmful impacts of fake news as well as the motivation mentioned in the previous sections lead to find a working and sustainable solution towards fake news detection and prevention. Since fake news detection is the main concern of this work, objectives can be summarized as follows:

- To detect fake news within a static dataset with the help of Supervised Machine Learning algorithms
- To evaluate the performances shown by different classifiers used for the specific dataset
- To propose a fake news model based on experimental results

1.6 Organization

The rest of this literature is organized as follows: in Chapter 2, existing solutions to Fake News problem are discussed briefly along with literature review. Chapter 3 of this literature contains few background studies for readers' benefits to understand the implementation and the entire work easily. Working principles of the algorithms used are discussed in this chapter. Besides, Chapter 4 demonstrates the methodology for fake news detection. Implementation of this methodology with all of its steps is also included here. Chapter 5 illustrates the results found from implementation and based on the results, performances of different classifiers are measured and analyzed. Finally, Chapter 6 concludes with discussion and states future work. Besides, based on the empirical results, a fake news model is proposed to implement in future. At the end of the literature, references are included.

Chapter 2

Related Work

In this chapter, some of the existing solutions to fake news problem are discussed. The working principles behind these solutions are briefly described. Pros and cons of each of these systems are also included. How a fact checking system can contribute to mitigate fake news problem is shown. Besides, related literature works are mentioned with notable significant contributions and claims. Since the fake news problem is a bit newer problem, the literature review mostly contains very recent works.

This chapter includes the following topics:

- Existing Solutions to Fake News Problem
 - FactCheck.org
 - B.S. Detector
- Literature Review

2.1 Existing Solutions to Fake News Problem

There are not many solutions proposed to fight against fake news problem. To date, two well known solutions regarding fake news problem are found: FactCheck.org and B.S Detector. These two solutions are described bellow:

2.1.1 FactCheck.org

Fact checking is the act of checking factual assertions in non-fictional text in order to determine the veracity and correctness of the factual statements in the text. This may be done either before or after the text has been published. FactCheck.org is a nonprofit and non-partisan website that describes itself as a “consumer advocate for voters that aims to reduce the level of deception and confusion in U.S. politics” [7]. It is a project of the Annenberg Public Policy Center of the Annenberg School for Communication at the University of Pennsylvania, and is funded primarily by the Annenberg Foundation. FactCheck.org has won four Webby Awards in the Politics category in 2008, 2010, 2011 and 2012. [9]

This solution is not directly related to fake news detection. However, by checking the fact claimed by a news it can be decided whether the news is real or fake.

Positive sides of this website are as follows: [10]

- Provides a longer summary of topic statement than other sites
- Cites where information comes from
- Generally lengthy discussion of topic
- Some tags are listed at end of topic
- Allows reader to ask questions of Factcheck
- Archives set up by person or topic

These advantages provided by this website have made it a good choice for fact checking though it can not meet up the demand to fight against fake news problem.

Moreover, this site has some limitations as well.

Limitations of this website can be summarized as follows: [10]

- have to click on summary to see full item discussion
- does not state on summary page what is fact or not
- does not provide a ranking system of truthfulness of topic
- no advanced search for topic, author, etc - only word or phrase search
- does not discuss methodology of fact-finding

Though number of fact checking websites is increasing now-a-days, FactCheck.org is still the most popular.

2.1.2 B. S. Detector

This is a browser extension which alerts its users about unreliable news sources. The B.S. Detector [8] is powered by OpenSources, a professionally curated list of unreliable or otherwise questionable sources. This does no longer maintains their own dataset. The B.S. Detector does not assume liability for the accuracy of OpenSources' data. This extension was initially blocked by Facebook which increases its popularity over night.

This extension is able to classify an unreliable news as fake news, satire, extreme bias etc. However, this classification is not reliable as they maintain a manual list of unreliable news sources. Since there is no arrangement of automatic indication of the unreliable news sources, it does not ensure reliability and competency. A news source which is listed as reliable in their manually compiled list can suddenly starts preaching fake news. Moreover, an unreliable news source may not always spread fake news. There is no such way to verify automatically whether a news is fake or reliable without matching the news source with their manual list. This seems as the biggest drawback of this extension.

Pros of this extension are:

- First browser extension that alerts about unreliable news source
- It can classify an unreliable news into its subcategory

On the other hand, cons of this browser extension can be summarized as follows:

- Maintains just a manually compiled list
- Provides no automatic method to detect fake news

In spite of the presence of some other fact checking systems, it does not seem that they are sufficient to spot fake news automatically and in a reliable manner. Hence, efforts should be put on in quest of a reliable fake news detection method.

2.2 Literature Review

Since the problem is relatively newer, there are not that much literature related to this. However, some of the latest works can be mentioned:

Rubin et al. focused on deception detection for news introducing three types of fake news [3]. Requirements for fake news detection corpus was also briefly explained by them.

Spivey et al. proposed a network approach [11]. How rumors turn into fake news in social media was shown by them. Besides, they also considered some psychological aspects to show that after few sequential transmissions a rumor may turn into a fake news.

Conroy et al. surveyed some state of the art technologies [12]. They focused on mainly two approaches - Linguistic approach and Network approach. Besides, they claimed that these two approaches have shown higher accuracy in classification tasks.

Narwa et al. proposed a very promising approach by proposing an automated assistant [13]. They claimed that this assistant is able to spot visual bias in news. They also proposed to consider Images attached with a news to detect if there is any visual bias.

Farajtabar et al. proposed a framework to mitigate fake news in social networks [14]. They combined reinforcement learning with a point process network activity

model. They mapped the fake news mitigation problem into a reinforcement learning framework. Moreover, they claimed that their proposed method shows a promising accuracy in real time fake news detection and outperformed the alternatives.

Conti et al. focused on proving how difficult it is to detect misinformation in social networks like Facebook [15]. Specially, they focused on spotting conspiracy theories stated as Facebook posts. They claimed that considering only structural analysis of a news is not sufficient to detect misinformation within it due to the veracity of misinformation types. Besides, they proved that for classification mechanism F1-score never exceeds 0.65 while identifying conspiracies.

Singhania et al. proposed a Deep Neural Network for fake news detection [16]. They named their model as 3HAN (Three Level Hierarchical Attention Network) which consists of 3 levels each for words, sentences and news headline. They got a higher accuracy of 96.77% on a large real world dataset as they claimed.

Ruchansky et al. proposed a model called CSI. This is composed of three different modules: Capture, Score, and Integrate [17]. The first module uses a Recurrent Neural Network (RNN) to capture the temporal pattern of user activity that occurred with a given article, and the second captures the behavior of users over time. The two are then integrated with the third module to classify an article as fake or not. Through experimental analysis on real-world data, they demonstrated that CSI achieves higher accuracy than existing models.

Jamil et al. proposed a framework to enhance the accuracy of machine learning based models for deception detection [18]. They believe that headline plays more important role than contents of a news to differentiate between real and deceptive news.

Sirajudeen et al. proposed a framework by which they showed necessary elements to build a fake news detector [19]. They put more emphasis on network approach for fake news detection.

Despite of the existence of the above related works, it seems that no of the existing works combined Linguistic and Network approach to build a model while most of them only considered machine learning based Linguistic approach.

Chapter 3

Background Study

This chapter provides background study which is expected to be helpful for readers to understand the implementation. As mentioned earlier, this chapter describes some of the supervised machine learning classification algorithms: Support Vector Machine (SVM), Logistic Regression (LR) and Stochastic Gradient Descent (SGD) which have been used during implementation in the next chapter.

Chapter 3 includes the following topics:

- Support Vector Machine (SVM)
 - Working Principle of SVM
 - * Linear Kernel
 - * Polynomial Kernel
 - * Gaussian Kernel
 - * Exponential Kernel
- Logistic Regression (LR)
- Stochastic Gradient Descent (SGD)

3.1 Support Vector Machine (SVM)

Support Vector Machine is one of the most popular machine learning algorithms. They were extremely popular around the time they were developed in the 1990s and still continue to be the go-to method for a high-performing algorithm with little tuning. Support Vector Machine (SVM) is a supervised machine learning algorithm which can be used for both classification or regression challenges. However, it is mostly used in classification problems.

3.1.1 Working Principle of SVM

A SVM is defined by a separating hyperplane. More specifically, for given labeled training data, the algorithm outputs a hyperplane which categorizes new examples. There are a good number of variants of SVM: proximal Support Vector Machines, probabilistic Support Vector Machines (PSVM) and fuzzy Support Vector Machines (FSVM). The operation of the SVM algorithm is based on finding the hyperplane that gives the largest minimum distance to the training examples. This distance receives important name of margin within SVM's theory. Therefore, the optimal separating hyperplane maximizes the margin of the training data. Hence, this classifier is also called as a large margin classifier.

Figure 3.1: Working Principle of SVM (Adapted from [20])

Figure 3.1 represents the working principle of Support Vector Machine. This works properly based on a trick called 'Kernel Trick' which is actually a function measuring similarity using dot products.

- **Linear Kernel:** For linear kernel the equation for prediction for a new input using the dot product between the input (x) and each support vector (x_i) is calculated as follows:

$$f(x) = B_0 + \sum (a_i * (x, x_i)) \quad (3.1)$$

This is an equation that involves calculating the inner products of a new input vector (x) with all support vectors in training data. The coefficients B_0 and a_i (for each input) must be estimated from the training data by the learning algorithm. More simply, the Linear kernel is the simplest kernel function. It is given by the inner product $\langle x, y \rangle$ plus an optional constant c which can be stated as follows:

$$k(x, y) = x^T y + c \quad (3.2)$$

Where, x and y are two vectors and x^T denotes transpose of vector x .

- **Polynomial Kernel:** The Polynomial kernel is a non-stationary kernel. This type of kernels are well suited for problems where all the training data is normalized. It works based on the following equation:

$$k(x, y) = (\alpha x^T y + c)^d \quad (3.3)$$

Where, α denotes the slope, d denotes the degree of polynomial and c is the constant.

- **Gaussian Kernel:** The Gaussian kernel is an example of radial basis function. A radial basis function (RBF) is a real-valued function whose value depends only on the distance from the origin. Gaussian kernel works according to the following equation:

$$K(x, x') = \exp\left(-\frac{\|x - x'\|^2}{2\sigma^2}\right) \quad (3.4)$$

Where, x and x' are two samples.

- **Exponential Kernel:** The exponential kernel is closely related to the Gaussian kernel, with only the square of the norm left out. It is also a radial basis function kernel.

For two samples x and x' Exponential Kernel works as follows:

$$K(x, x') = \exp\left(-\frac{\|x - x'\|^2}{2\sigma^2}\right) \quad (3.5)$$

3.2 Logistic Regression (LR)

Logistic regression (LR) is another technique borrowed by machine learning from the field of statistics. It is the go-to method for binary classification problems (problems with two class values). The activation function of a node defines the output of that node given an input or set of inputs. Logistic Regression classifier uses Sigmoid function as activation function. Sigmoid function returns a value between 0 and 1 as shown in the following Figure 3.2:

Figure 3.2: Sigmoid Activation Function

In order to map this value in a discrete class, a threshold value is defined. For example, if 0.5 is assumed as the threshold, values returned from sigmoid function greater than or equal to 0.5 will be considered as class 1. On the contrary, values less than 0.5 will be considered as class 0.

Sigmoid function returns the output value based on the following equation:

$$\phi(z) = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-z}} \quad (3.6)$$

Where, z is an input sample of the Sigmoid function.

Concretely, class of a random sample z is defined as follows:

$$\text{Class of } z = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } \phi(z) \geq 0.5 \\ 0, & \text{if } \phi(z) < 0.5 \end{cases}$$

3.3 Stochastic Gradient Descent (SGD)

Stochastic gradient descent is a stochastic approximation of gradient descent [21]. Even though SGD has been around in the machine learning community for a long time, it has received a considerable amount of attention just recently in the context of large-scale learning. A good reason behind choosing this classifier is: SGD has been successfully applied to large-scale and sparse machine learning problems often encountered in text classification and natural language processing. Given that the data is sparse, the classifiers in this module easily scale to problems with more than 10^5 training examples and more than 10^5 features. Since there is possibility that sparse data can be generated after feature extraction using BOW model, it is expected that this classifier will take comparatively less time than other classifiers. Complexity of this classifier can be defined as: If X is a matrix of size (n, p) , then training has a cost of $O(kn\bar{p})$, where k is the number of iterations (epochs) and \bar{p} is the average number of non-zero attributes per sample.

Using the Gradient Decent (GD) optimization algorithm, the weights are updated incrementally after each epoch (= pass over the training dataset). The cost function J , the Sum of Squared Errors (SSE), can be written as:

$$J(w) = \frac{1}{2} \sum_i (target^{(i)} - output^{(i)})^2 \quad (3.7)$$

The magnitude and direction of the weight update is computed by taking a step in the opposite direction of the cost gradient:

$$\Delta w_j = -\eta \frac{\delta J}{\delta w_j} \quad (3.8)$$

Where, η is the learning rate. The weights are then updated after each epoch via the following update rule:

$$w := w + \Delta w \quad (3.9)$$

Further study on this supervised machine learning algorithm can be done from [21].

Chapter 4

Methodology and Implementation

This chapter discusses the methodology followed during implementation. All of the phases of implementation are described steps by steps here. Different NLP (Natural Language Processing) models used in feature extraction are also included here.

This chapter includes the following topics:

- Methodology
- Experimental Setup
- Dataset Collection
- Data Preprocessing
- Feature Extraction
 - Bag of Words(BOW) model
 - N - gram Model
 - TF - IDF Model
- Applying Classifiers

4.1 Methodology

From the literature review done in Chapter 2, it is clear that to get higher accuracy than existing models, Deep learning concepts have to be employed as works based on Deep models showed better performance. However, due to the limitation of state of the art hardware technology like GPU, applying any Deep model is almost impossible at this stage. Besides, about applying Machine Learning based Linguistic models, considering the memory limit, large scale real datasets can not be used. As a result, implementation will be limited to Machine Learning based Linguistic models on a smaller dataset. However, to the best of knowledge, this is going to be the first ever implementation on the dataset considered.

A general purpose text classification model is applied on the dataset. Methodology followed during implementation can be shown as follows:

Figure 4.1: Block Diagram of the Methodology Followed

Figure 4.1 shows a basic text classification approach based on machine learning. The implementation follows this methodology where few classifiers are applied and analyzed based on comparison of their performances.

Implementation consists of the following steps:

- Experimental Setup
- Dataset Collection
- Data Preprocessing
- Feature Extraction
- Applying Classifiers

The above mentioned steps during implementation are described in the following sections:

4.2 Experimental Setup

Throughout the implementation, all the experiments were done on Intel Core i5 CPU. It had a processor speed of 3.2 GHz and a 4 GB of RAM was associated with this. A machine learning library called 'Scikit-learn' [22] was used. Actually, 'Scikit-learn' is a free library for the Python programming language. Besides, another two libraries of the same programming language called 'NumPy' [23] and 'Pandas' [24] were used. 'NumPy' supports large, multi-dimensional arrays and matrices, along with a large collection of high-level mathematical functions to operate on these arrays. On the other hand, 'Pandas' offers data structures and operations for manipulating numerical tables which was actually used for loading the dataset.

4.3 Dataset Collection

Since, the problem is relatively newer and more recent, not too many datasets related to that problem were found at the time we started working. Hence, dataset collection was one of the toughest phases of the entire work. With the passage of time, the fake news problem was being popular day by day and getting more sensation. Therefore, a few datasets were found; however, they are not suitable to be implemented with limited hardware resources. Some of them are too large (about 1 GB) in size exceeding the existing memory limits while some are not publicly available. Eventually, a dataset [25] was chosen which is suitable to implement with the help of existing hardware resource. At the same time, this dataset is publicly available which ensures free access to this dataset. This dataset was found in GitHub as a repository. A journalist later turned to a data scientist named George McIntire uploaded this on February 25, 2017. He stated nothing much than this dataset was prepared for his own Fake Vs Real news project. This dataset is available in GitHub as a .zip file of 11.3 MB. In the above experimental setup, after extracting the .zip file it took 29.2 MB size on disk.

This dataset contains 7795 instances where each instance represents a news article. There are 2 attributes: ('Title' and 'Text'. 'Title' shows the headline or title of a news and 'Text' contains the body text or details of a news. For each instance there is a 'Label' that defines whether the news article is 'REAL' or 'FAKE'.

Table 4.1: Brief Specification of the Dataset Used

Total No. of Instances	7795
Total No. of Attributes	2
Total No. of Classes	2
Type of Instance	News article
Attributes	Title, Text
Attribute 1 (Title)	Represents the news headline
Attribute 2 (Text)	Contains the news details
Class Labels	REAL, FAKE

Table 4.1 illustrates a brief specification of the dataset [25] used.

4.4 Data Preprocessing

Data preprocessing was performed according to the following manners:

- Dataset (.csv format) was loaded using 'Pandas' library.
- Parsing was done to extract meaningful string and syntax from the dataset.
- After that, only letters were considered from the parsed items.
- Each letter was converted to lower case.
- Then a list of words was created splitting words consisting of only lower case letters.
- Next, stopwords (e.g. 'a', 'and', 'but', 'how', 'that' etc.) are removed using NLTK (Natural Language ToolKit - a suite of libraries and programs for symbolic and statistical Natural Language Processing for English). [26]

Changes after the data preprocessing on a single news article can be shown as Figure 4.2 at the following page:

<p>Google Pinterest Digg Linkedin Reddit Stumbleupon Print Delicious Pocket Tumblr</p> <p>There are two fundamental truths in this world: Paul Ryan desperately wants to be president. And Paul Ryan will never be president. Today proved it.</p> <p>In a particularly staggering example of political cowardice, Paul Ryan re-re-re-reversed course and announced that he was back on the Trump Train after all. This was an aboutface from where he was a few weeks ago. He had previously declared he would not be supporting or defending Trump after a tape was made public in which Trump bragged about assaulting women. Suddenly, Ryan was appearing at a pro-Trump rally and boldly declaring that he already sent in his vote to make him President of the United States. It was a surreal moment. The figurehead of the Republican Party dosed himself in gasoline, got up on a stage on a chilly afternoon in Wisconsin, and lit a match. . @SpeakerRyan says he voted for @realDonaldTrump : “Republicans, it is time to come home” https://t.co/VyTT49YvoE pic.twitter.com/wCvSCg4a5I</p> <p>— ABC News Politics (@ABCPolitics) November 5, 2016</p> <p>The Democratic Party couldn’t have asked for a better moment of film. Ryan’s chances of ever becoming president went down to zero in an instant. In the wreckage Trump is to leave behind in his wake, those who cravenly backed his campaign will not recover. If Ryan’s career manages to limp all the way to 2020, then the DNC will have this tape locked and loaded to be used in every ad until Election Day. The ringing endorsement of the man he clearly hates on a personal level speaks volumes about his own spinelessness. Ryan has postured himself as a “principled” conservative, and one uncomfortable with Trump’s unapologetic bigotry and sexism. However, when push came to shove, Paul Ryan – like many of his colleagues – turned into a sniveling appeaser. After all his lofty tak about conviction, his principles were a house of cards and collapsed with the slightest breeze.</p> <p>What’s especially bizarre is how close Ryan came to making it through unscathed. For months the Speaker of the House refused to comment on Trump at all. His strategy seemed to be to keep his head down, pretend Trump didn’t exist, and hope that nobody remembered what happened in 2016. Now, just days away from the election, he screwed it all up.</p> <p>If 2016’s very ugly election has done any good it’s by exposing the utter cowardice of the Republicans who once feigned moral courage. A reality television star spit on them, hijacked their party, insulted their wives, and got every last one of them to kneel before him. What a turn of events.</p> <p>Featured image via Twitter</p>	<p>google pinterest digg linkedin reddit stumbleupon print delicious pocket tumblr two fundamental truths world paul ryan desperately wants president paul ryan never president today proved particularly staggering example political cowardice paul ryan reversed course announced back trump train aboutface weeks ago previously declared would supporting defending trump tape made public trump bragged assaulting women suddenly ryan appearing pro trump rally boldly declaring already sent vote make president united states surreal moment figurehead republican party dosed gasoline got stage chilly afternoon wisconsin lit match speakerryan says voted realdonaldtrump republicans time come home https://t.co/VyTT49YvoE abc news politics abcpolitics november democratic party asked better moment film ryan chances ever becoming president went zero instant wreckage trump leave behind wake cravenly backed campaign recover ryan career manages limp way dnc tape locked loaded used every ad election day ringing endorsement man clearly hates personal level speaks volumes spinelessness ryan postured principled conservative one uncomfortable trump unapologetic bigotry sexism however push came shove paul ryan like many colleagues turned sniveling appeaser lofty tak conviction principles house cards collapsed slightest breeze especially bizarre close ryan came making unscathed months speaker house refused comment trump strategy seemed keep head pretend trump exist hope nobody remembered happened days away election screwed ugly election done good exposing utter cowardice republicans feigned moral courage reality television star spit hijacked party insulted wives got every last one kneel turn events featured image via twitter</p>
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Figure 4.2: A News Article Before(left) and After(right) Data Preprocessing

4.5 Feature Extraction

Feature extraction is an attribute reduction process. It results in a much smaller and richer set of attributes. Feature extraction refers to the transformation of input data into a set of features where features are distinctive properties of input patterns that help in differentiating between the categories of input patterns. It is also a process that derives new features from the original features to reduce the cost of feature measurement and increase classifier efficiency. In case of this work, feature extraction refers to extraction of linguistic items from the documents to provide a representative sample of their content. Distinctive vocabulary items found in a document are assigned to the different categories by measuring the importance of those items to the document content.

Feature extraction was done on 3000 news articles of the dataset. More than that could not be considered due to the memory limit. Feature extraction was performed using few models of Natural Language Processing (NLP): Bag of Words(BOW) model, n-gram model and TF-IDF model. These three models are discussed in the subsections under this section.

4.5.1 Bag of Words(BOW) model

The bag-of-words model is a way of representing text data when modeling text with machine learning algorithms. It is simple to understand and implement. According to this model of Natural Language Processing, any text or document is represented by a bag which is full of words. In this case, order of appearing a word in the text is not considered. After that, one or more consecutive words are picked from the bag and number of their occurrences (frequency) is treated as a feature. This model was chosen as it is a kind of representation which has several successful applications such as sentiment analysis [27], spam detection [28] and so on. Working principle of Bag of Words(BOW) model consists of:

1. A vocabulary of known words.
2. A measure of the presence of known words.

4.5.2 N-gram Model

N -gram model is often associated with Bag of Words (BOW) model. The value of ‘ N ’ in N -gram model defines the number of consecutive words to be considered while counting their frequencies. If one single word is used then it is called Unigram ($N=1$). In Bigram ($N=2$) model, two consecutive words are considered. Similarly, value of ‘ N ’ is decided based on specific cases.

4.5.3 Bag of Words N-gram Model

Bag of Words(BOW) and N -gram models are often used together. Usually, they were combined during feature extraction. An example of applying Bag of Words(BOW) N -gram model is shown bellow:

- Sentence 1: This news seems to be authentic.
- Sentence 2: If this news is not real, it is a fake news.

After data preprocessing is done, this {‘News’, ‘Seem’, ‘Authentic’, ‘Real’, ‘Fake’} set of unique words is found according to Bag of Words model. Now, Unigram model is applied and word frequencies are counted as follows:

Table 4.2: Feature Extraction using BOW, Unigram Model

	News	Seem	Authentic	Real	Fake
Sentence 1	1	1	1	0	0
Sentence 2	2	0	0	1	1

Table 4.2 illustrates an example of feature extraction using BOW Unigram ($N = 1$) model. In this example, for the sentence the word news appears for only one time and so is counted. Again, in the second sentence, the same word news appears for twice. Hence, frequency of the word is counted as 2. Thus, using BOW N -gram model, feature extraction is performed where text to vectorization is performed.

4.5.4 TF - IDF Model

A problem with scoring word frequency is highly frequent words start to dominate in the document (e.g. larger score), but may not contain as much “informational content”

to the model as rarer but perhaps domain specific words.

One approach is to rescale the frequency of words by how often they appear in all documents, so that the scores for frequent words like “the” that are also frequent across all documents are penalized.

TF - IDF stands for Term Frequency – Inverse Document Frequency which is a numerical statistic that is intended to reflect how important a word is to a document in a collection or corpus. It consists of the following:

- Term Frequency: This is a scoring of the frequency of the word in the current document. It is calculated in the same way of Bag of Words model.
- Inverse Document Frequency: This is a scoring of how rare the word is across documents.

If $N=|D|$ is the total number of documents in the corpus and $|\{d \in D : t \in d\}|$ is the number of documents where the term t appears,

$$idf(t, d) = \log \frac{N}{1 + |\{d \in D : t \in d\}|} \quad (4.1)$$

Finally, Term Frequency and Inverse Document Frequency are multiplied to build the TF - IDF model.

4.6 Applying Classifiers

At this phase of implementation, chosen classifiers are applied on the features from the dataset along with the labels. Due to the most frequent use in different text classification problems, Support Vector Machine (SVM), Logistic Regression (LR) and Stochastic Gradient Descent (SGD) classifiers were selected to apply on the dataset after data preprocessing and feature extraction are done.

2000 News articles were used for training classification algorithms and the rest 1000 news articles were used for testing the performances of classifiers. Performances of the classifiers are measured and recorded which has been shown in the next chapter.

Chapter 5

Experimental Results & Analysis

Chapter 5 presents all the experimental results using tabular and graphical format. At the beginning, some of the metrics used to measure the performance of a classifier are briefly discussed. Among them, Precision(P), Recall(R), F1 Score are the most important which are actually calculated using True Positive(TP), True Negative(TN), False Positive(FP) and False Negative(FN).

Experimental results found from both the Bag of Words(BOW) and TF-IDF (Term Frequency-Inverse Document Frequency) models with two of their variants Unigram and Bigram for N -gram model have been clearly illustrated with brief discussion on each table and figure. Cross validation is done to validate the models. At the end of this chapter, a summary of the Experimental Result Analysis has been included.

After all, this chapter includes the following contents:

- Metrics to Measure Experimental Results
- Experimental Results on Applying Models
 - Results Obtained by BOW N -gram Model
 - Comparison between BOW Unigram and Bigram Model
 - Results Obtained by TF-IDF N -gram Model
 - Comparison between TF-IDF Unigram and Bigram Model
- Cross Validation
- Summary of Experimental Result Analysis

5.1 Metrics to Measure Experimental Results

While recording experimental results obtained by different models, the following four metrics were considered:

1. True Positive (TP): It means the total number of correct predictions such that an instance is positive. If the prediction is positive and the actual output is also positive, then it is a true positive.
2. True Negative (TN): It refers to the total number of correct predictions that an instance is negative. If the prediction is negative and the actual output is also negative, then it is a true negative.
3. False Positive (FP): It means the total number of incorrect predictions that an instance is positive. If the prediction is positive but the actual output is negative, then it is a false positive.
4. False Negative (FN): It denotes the total number of incorrect predictions that an instance is negative. If the prediction is negative but the actual output is positive, then it is a false negative.

These four metrics are called the elements of confusion matrix from which the overall performance of a classifier can be measured.

Table 5.1: Confusion Matrix

	Predicted: NO	Predicted: YES
Actual: NO	True Negative (TN)	False Positive (FP)
Actual: YES	False Negative (FN)	True Positive (TP)

Table 5.1 represents the confusion matrix and its four elements which are defined.

Based on the elements of this matrix mentioned earlier, performance of classifiers can be measured. There are another four metrics to indicate the overall performance of a classification algorithm.

These other four performance measuring metrics mentioned in the previous page are briefly described here:

1. Precision (P): Precision provides idea about how much positive predictions are correct and is defined as:

$$P = \frac{TP}{TP + FP} \quad (5.1)$$

2. Recall (R): Recall denotes how much positive cases are correctly predicted and is defined as:

$$R = \frac{TP}{TP + FN} \quad (5.2)$$

3. F1 Score: It is defined as the harmonic mean of Precision(P) and Recall(R).

$$F1 = 2 \times \frac{P \times R}{P + R} \quad (5.3)$$

4. Accuracy: Accuracy refers to how much predictions are accurate. It is usually measured in percentage(%) as:

$$Accuracy(\%) = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + TN + FP + FN} \times 100 \quad (5.4)$$

All the above metrics are calculated with the help of the elements of confusion matrix.

5.2 Experimental Results on Applying Models

At this stage, models discussed in the previous chapter are applied on the the dataset. As mentioned earlier, two Natural Language Processing models: BOW (Bag of Words) and TF-IDF (Term Frequency-Inverse Document Frequency) associated with another model N -gram are applied during implementation. Experimental results found for models are listed bellow:

5.2.1 Results Obtained by BOW N -gram Model

BOW model which is considered as one of the successful model used in text classification problems has come with 2 varieties: BOW Unigram ($N = 1$) and BOW Bigram ($N = 2$). These two combinations are applied one by one and experimental results found for different classifiers are recorded.

Table 5.2: Experimental Results on Using Unigram Model

Classifier	True Positive (TP)	True Negative (TN)	False Positive (FP)	False Negative (FN)
Support Vector Machine (SVM) - Linear Kernel	429	442	76	53
Logistic Regression (LR)	450	440	78	32
Stochastic Gradient Descent (SGD)	422	455	63	60

Table 5.2 shows the total number of True Positive, True Negative, False Positive and False Negative news articles. From the table it can be seen that among three classifiers, Logistic Regression has highest number of True Positive and True Negative news articles. That means it has classified the real news as real and fake news as fake more accurately compared to others. Besides, it has the lowest number of False Negative which is an indication of least misclassification. Based on the data of this table, Precision, Recall, F1 score and Accuracy of the classifiers will be calculated.

Table 5.3: Performances of Classifiers for BOW Unigram Model

Classifier	Precision (P) $P=TP/(TP+FP)$	Recall (R) $R=TP/(TP+FN)$	F1 Score $=\frac{2*P*R}{P+R}$	Accuracy (%)
Support Vector Machine (SVM) - Linear Kernel	0.849	0.890	0.869	87.1
Logistic Regression (LR)	0.852	0.934	0.891	89
Stochastic Gradient Descent (SGD)	0.870	0.875	0.872	87.7

Table 5.3 shows the performances on classifiers for fake news detection using BOW Unigram model during feature extraction. As expected from the data of previous Table 5.2, Logistic Regression shows the highest accuracy among all three classifiers. Besides, other metrics like Precision, Recall and F1 score are also found highest in case of Logistic Regression. Since the higher value of these metrics indicate the better performance of a classifier, it can be said that Logistic Regression outperforms the other two classifiers for the model and dataset considered.

Table 5.4: Experimental Results on Using BOW Bigram Model

Classifier	True Positive (TP)	True Negative (TN)	False Positive (FP)	False Negative (FN)
Support Vector Machine (SVM) - Linear Kernel	440	439	79	42
Logistic Regression (LR)	461	450	68	21
Stochastic Gradient Descent (SGD)	433	447	71	49

Table 5.4 presents results observed by applying classifiers on features extracted using BOW Bigram ($N = 2$) model. This table also indicates that Logistic Regression has still got the highest number of True Positive and True Negative news articles. This time it has also got the least number of misclassification that is the minimum number of False Positive and False Negative news articles compared to other classification algorithms. Hence, considering Bigram model instead of Unigram has decreased the number of classifications for this classifier. Therefore, increasing in accuracy is also expected.

Table 5.5: Performances of Classifiers for BOW Bigram Model

Classifier	Precision (P) $P=TP/(TP+FP)$	Recall (R) $R=TP/(TP+FN)$	F1 Score $= (2*P*R)/(P+R)$	Accuracy (%)
Support Vector Machine (SVM) - Linear Kernel	0.848	0.912	0.879	87.9
Logistic Regression (LR)	0.871	0.956	0.912	91.1
Stochastic Gradient Descent (SGD)	0.859	0.898	0.878	88

Table 5.5 shows that considering counting the frequencies of two consecutive words instead of a single word for feature extraction has increased performances of all the three classifiers. For instance, accuracy of SVM with Linear Kernel has been increased from 87.1% to 87.9%. Besides, accuracy of Stochastic Gradient Descent (SGD) is also increased from 87.7% to 88%. On the other hand, Logistic regression shows a accuracy of 91.1% which is so far the highest accuracy found for the dataset considered.

5.2.2 Comparison between BOW Unigram and Bigram Model

So far the experimental results found, it is clear that classifiers outperform themselves while using Bigram model for feature extraction instead of Unigram model. Besides, the highest accuracy achieved for Logistic Regression is obtained by using Bigram model where frequency of two consecutive words are counted for conversion of text data into numerical data.

Table 5.6: Performances of Classifiers for Unigram and Bigram Models

Classifier	Accuracy (Unigram) %	Accuracy (Bigram) %
Support Vector Machine (SVM) - Linear Kernel	87.1	87.9
Logistic Regression (LR)	89	91.1
Stochastic Gradient Descent (SGD)	87.7	88

Table 5.6 shows comparison of classifiers' performances for Unigram model and Bigram model. Not only the highest performing classifier Logistic Regression but also the other two classifiers also outperform their performances while using Bigram model in lieu of Unigram model.

Figure 5.1: Comparison of Classifiers' Performances for Unigram & Bigram Models

Figure 5.1 shows a comparison among the performances of classifiers for models; however, the highest accuracy till now is given by Logistic Regression (LR).

5.2.3 Results Obtained by TF-IDF N-gram Model

Beside, BOW and another model of Natural Language Processing: TF-IDF is applied as mentioned earlier. This model also comes with two varieties- Unigram and Bigram.

Table 5.7: Experimental Results on Using TF-IDF Unigram Model

Classifier	True Positive (TP)	True Negative (TN)	False Positive (FP)	False Negative (FN)
Support Vector Machine (SVM) - Linear Kernel	455	455	63	27
Logistic Regression (LR)	448	462	56	34
Stochastic Gradient Descent (SGD)	449	455	63	33

Table 5.7 shows the total number of True Positive, True Negative, False Positive and False Negative news articles obtained using TF-IDF Unigram model. From the table it can be seen that among three classifiers, Logistic Regression has highest number of True Negative news articles. That means it has classified the real news as real more accurately compared to others. Besides, SVM with Linear Kernel has the highest number of True Positive news articles and lowest number of False Negative articles. Based on the data of this table, Precision, Recall, F1 score and Accuracy of the classifiers will be calculated.

Table 5.8: Performances of Classifiers for TF-IDF Unigram Model

Classifier	Precision (P) $P=TP/(TP+FP)$	Recall (R) $R=TP/(TP+FN)$	F1 Score $=(2*P*R)/(P+R)$	Accuracy (%)
Support Vector Machine (SVM) - Linear Kernel	0.878	0.944	0.910	91
Logistic Regression (LR)	0.889	0.929	0.908	91
Stochastic Gradient Descent (SGD)	0.877	0.932	0.903	90.4

Table 5.8 shows the performances on classifiers for fake news detection using TF-IDF Unigram model during feature extraction. Based on the data of Table 5.7, Logistic Regression and SVM with linear kernel show relatively better accuracy than SGD.

Table 5.9: Experimental Results on Using TF-IDF Bigram Model

Classifier	True Positive (TP)	True Negative (TN)	False Positive (FP)	False Negative (FN)
Support Vector Machine (SVM) - Linear Kernel	453	456	62	29
Logistic Regression (LR)	457	463	55	25
Stochastic Gradient Descent (SGD)	443	455	63	39

Table 5.9 represents experimental results observed by applying classifiers using TF-IDF Bigram ($N = 2$) model. This table also indicates that Logistic Regression has got the highest number of True Positive and True Negative news articles. This time it has also got the least number of misclassification that is the minimum number of False Positive and False Negative news articles compared to other classification algorithms. Hence, considering Bigram model instead of Unigram has decreased the number of misclassifications for this classifier. Increasing in accuracy of Logistic Regression is expected.

Table 5.10: Performances of Classifiers for TF-IDF Bigram Model

Classifier	Precision (P) $P=TP/(TP+FP)$	Recall (R) $R=TP/(TP+FN)$	F1 Score $= (2 * P * R) / (P + R)$	Accuracy (%)
Support Vector Machine (SVM) - Linear Kernel	0.879	0.939	0.908	90.9
Logistic Regression (LR)	0.892	0.948	0.919	92
Stochastic Gradient Descent (SGD)	0875	0919	0.897	89.8

Table 5.10 shows that considering counting the frequencies of two consecutive words instead of a single word for feature extraction has increased performances of Logistic Regression. For instance, accuracy has increased from 91% to 92% for this classifier. However, accuracy of SVM with Linear Kernel has been decreased from 91% to 90.9%. Besides, accuracy of Stochastic Gradient Descent (SGD) has also decreased from 90.4% to 89.8%. Therefore, the 92% accuracy shown by Logistic regression can be considered as the new highest which exceeds the 91% accuracy for previous model.

5.2.4 Comparison between TF-IDF Unigram and Bigram Model

After obtaining the experimental results by applying both the Unigram and Bigram variants of TF-IDF language model, performances shown by classifiers are compared between these two varieties.

Table 5.11: Performances of Classifiers for Unigram and Bigram Models

Classifier	Accuracy (Unigram) %	Accuracy (Bigram) %
Support Vector Machine (SVM) - Linear Kernel	91	90.9
Logistic Regression (LR)	91	92
Stochastic Gradient Descent (SGD)	90.4	89.8

Table 5.11 shows that performance of SVM and SGD decreases for considering Bigram instead of Unigram. On the other hand, Logistic Regression(LR) shows better accuracy in TF-IDF Bigram model than Unigram model. More specifically, for TF-IDF Bigram model Logistic Regression shows the highest accuracy ever on the used dataset.

Figure 5.2: Comparison of Classifiers' Performances for Unigram & Bigram Models

Figure 5.2 shows that the 92% accuracy shown by Logistic Regression for TF-IDF Bigram model is the highest ever accuracy on the dataset considered.

5.3 Cross Validation

Cross-validation which is also called rotation estimation,[29] is a model validation technique for assessing how the results of a statistical analysis will generalize to an independent data set. It is mainly used in settings where the goal is prediction, and one wants to estimate how accurately a predictive model will perform in practice. In a prediction problem, a model is usually given a dataset of known data on which training is run (training dataset), and a dataset of unknown data (or first seen data) against which the model is tested (called the validation dataset or testing set). [30]

To validate the experimental results, 10 Fold Cross Validation is done where 9 folds are used for training and the rest one is used for measuring testing accuracy repeating this for 10 times. After that, an average of these 10 results is taken.

Table 5.12: Cross Validation Accuracy for BOW Unigram and Bigram Models

Classifier	Accuracy (Unigram) %	CV Accuracy (Unigram) %	Accuracy (Bigram) %	CV Accuracy (Bigram) %
Support Vector Machine (SVM) - Linear Kernel	87.1	87.3	87.9	88.0
Logistic Regression (LR)	89	79.1	91.1	89.6
Stochastic Gradient Descent (SGD)	87.7	82.8	88	88.1

Table 5.12 shows both accuracy calculated from experimental results and accuracy of cross validation.

From this table, it is clear that Logistic Regression (LR) provides maximum 91.1% accuracy according to experimental results and 89.6% cross validation accuracy for BOW Bigram model. Since fake news detection is an ill-posed problem, performance shown by Logistic Regression(LR) is worth considering as satisfactory for the dataset considered.

Performances of SVM with linear kernel and Stochastic Gradient Descent vary from model to model during this implementation; however, Logistic Regression has been showing a reasonable performance from the beginning for both Unigram and Bigram model associated with BOW model.

Figure 5.3: Cross Validation for BOW Models

Figure 5.3 shows the graphical representation of the data shown in Table 5.12 where it can be clearly seen that Logistic Regression outperforms other classifiers with an accuracy of 91.1%.

Table 5.13: Cross Validation Accuracy for TF-IDF Unigram and Bigram Models

Classifier	Accuracy (Unigram) %	CV Accuracy (Unigram) %	Accuracy (Bigram) %	CV Accuracy (Bigram) %
Support Vector Machine (SVM) - Linear Kernel	91	90.1	90.2	88.0
Logistic Regression (LR)	91	91.2	92	91.4
Stochastic Gradient Descent (SGD)	90.4	89.2	89.8	84.5

Table 5.13 represents cross validation accuracy of each classifier for both the Unigram and Bigram model associated with Bag of Words model. It shows that the highest accuracy using Support Vector Machine with linear kernel is 91% for TF-IDF Unigram model. This accuracy decreases in Bigram model and in both the cross validations of Unigram and Bigram. Stochastic Gradient Descent is the lowest performer among all the three classifiers.

Figure 5.4: Cross Validation for BOW Models

Figure 5.4 represents the data of Table 5.13 graphically. From this figure, it is clearly seen that Logistic Regression outperforms the other two classifiers for both the models associated with TF-IDF model. Besides, Logistic Regression has an accuracy of 91% and 92% for Unigram and Bigram models respectively. Moreover, the cross validation accuracy obtained by this classifier is also relatively higher. For TF-IDF Unigram model, cross validation accuracy observed using Logistic Regression is 91.2% and for Bigram model which is 91.4%.

5.4 Summary of Experimental Result Analysis

So far the experimental results presented support that decision of using Bigram model instead of Unigram model increased the performances of all the three classifiers in case of BOW model. Because, words come as a sentence. Therefore, considering two consecutive words might be more meaningful than considering only a single word.

On the other hand, for TF-IDF model, not all the classifiers' performances follow the same sequence. Considering Bigram model increased the performance of Logistic Regression while Feature extraction using TF-IDF. However, about other classifiers, their performances were better during using Unigram model rather than Bigram.

The best performer among the classifiers considered is the Logistic Regression(LR) after considering both of the two models with their N -gram variants. For Bag of Words

Bigram model, accuracy of this classifier is 91.2% and 91% for TF-IDF Unigram model; however, for TF-IDF Bigram model, it exceeds all of the previous performances with an accuracy of 92% which can be considered as satisfactory for the dataset considered.

Though both the SVM with linear kernel and the Logistic Regression(LR) show the same accuracy, cross validation accuracy is higher for Logistic Regression. Moreover, the best cross validation accuracy while considering TF-IDF Bigram model is found for Logistic Regression classifier. Specifically, at that setting, the test set accuracy is 92% while the cross validation accuracy is 91.4%. Thus, Logistic Regression performs the best among all three classification algorithms on the dataset considered.

An accuracy of 92% observed by Logistic Regression is the highest ever on the dataset used. Moreover, this performance of Logistic Regression can be proposed as a benchmark for the dataset since this is the first ever implementation on this dataset and according to the best of knowledge, no other implementation is found on this recently released dataset.

Chapter 6

Discussion and Conclusion

This chapter concludes the literature. At the beginning of this chapter, the entire work is summarized. After that, some of the limitations during this work have been included. Findings of the research work done are also mentioned. The final section presents a General Purpose Fake News Model to indicate future work. Hopefully, this proposed model will be implemented in future given that proper real world dataset is found or any synthetic dataset is created.

This chapter concludes with the following contents:

- Summary
- Limitations
- Findings of this Research
- Future Work
 - Proposed Fake News Model for Future Implementation

6.1 Summary

In this era of big data containing lots of varieties and veracities, it is a very difficult task to differentiate between a real and fake news. On the other hand, building a real-time news verification suite needs prior successful model able to spot deception within static datasets. More specifically, a successful model in this case is expected to draw boundary between real and fake even in a real-time dynamic environment. This expectation has made the job very challenging to detect a fake news; however, this literature presents an implementation of fake news detection within a static dataset with the help of text classification algorithms based on supervised machine learning. Linguistic approach using Logistic Regression(LR) classifier provides an accuracy of 92% which is worth considering as satisfactory. Moreover, a general purpose fake news model combining Linguistic and Network approaches has also been proposed in a realization that only text classification approach may be proven insufficient in near future.

6.2 Limitations

The following items indicate some of the limitations faced during the thesis work:

- Applying Deep Learning approach could be the best way to consider for solving such an ill-posed problem like fake news detection; however, it could not be possible due to having no state of the art hardware technology like GPU.
- Memory limit was a big issue during implementation. Therefore, working with more than 3,000 news article could not be possible. Besides, similar but larger real world dataset could not be considered.
- The fake news model proposed under Section 6.4 could not be implemented and verified due to the scarcity of available dataset.
- Hyper-parameters of the classifiers could be tuned more to increase accuracy.

6.3 Findings of this Research

Findings of this research work inclined to search for a solution to fake news problem are as follows:

- Applying only Linguistic approach seems insufficient to reach at a reliable and sustainable solution for fake news problem.
- Employing Deep Learning approach may work better to find intrinsic patterns of words in sentences more accurately to differentiate fake news from a real news.
- Integrating a network approach to verify the source of a news may be a good choice.
- To build a reliable news verification or fake news detection system, models used to train classifiers need to be designed in a suitable manner to work in a dynamic real time environment.
- A reliable benchmark dataset containing real world news articles along with the headlines, body texts, sources and labels is needed for research purpose.

6.4 Future Work

In future, work may be done to create a dataset containing news articles. Besides, Deep Learning [31] approach may be employed to solve the fake news problem. Specifically, Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) and Recurrent Neural Network (RNN) can be used for both feature extraction and classification. Besides, while applying linguistic approach shown by this work, network approach can be combined to differentiate between real and fake news. Finally, the proposed general purpose fake news model may be improved and implemented.

6.4.1 Proposed Fake News Model for Future Implementation

By the end of this thesis work, there is a realization that in near future may be in few months or years, considering only machine learning based text classification will be proven insufficient for fake news detection. Hence, a novel general purpose fake news detection model is proposed that is not only news texts or contents oriented but also focused on the source of news.

Figure 6.1: Proposed Model for Fake News Detection

In this model, both linguistic and network approaches are merged. In linguistic part, model will be trained almost in the same way this literature does. Next, feature extraction will be applied on news title and texts. At the same time, features will be extracted from the information regarding news source using network approach. Next, features extracted from both the two approaches will be combined and then classifiers will be applied to get the determination whether a news article is real or fake.

This model will be improved and implemented in future. Hopefully, this novel general purpose model will contribute in building reliable news verification system.

References

- [1] “Fake News,” Wikipedia, The Free Encyclopedia. [Online]. Available: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Fake_news. [Last Accessed: Dec. 03, 2017].
- [2] “What is fake news,” Definition from WhatIs.com, 2017. [Online]. Available: <http://whatis.techtarget.com/definition/fake-news>. [Last Accessed: Dec. 03, 2017].
- [3] V. L. Rubin, Y. Chen, N. J. Conroy. “Deception detection for news: three types of fakes,” Proc. of the Assoc. for Inform. Sci. and Technology, vol. 52, pp 1-4, 2015.
- [4] C. L. Teck, “The negative impact of fake news,” The Daily Star, 2017. [Online] Available: <http://www.thedailystar.net/op-ed/the-negative-impact-fake-news-1401223>. [Last Accessed: Dec. 03, 2017].
- [5] B. Rohrer, “What Types of Question can Data Science Answer,” KDnuggets, 2015. [Online]. Available: <https://www.kdnuggets.com/2015/09/questions-data-science-can-answer.html>. [Last Accessed: Dec. 03, 2017].
- [6] “Supervised Machine Learning with a Support Vector Machine,” neos Guide. [Online]. Available: <https://neos-guide.org/content/supervised-machine-learning-support-vector-machine>. [Last Accessed: Dec. 03, 2017].
- [7] Bronxville, “Factcheck.org -- A Fraudulent "Fact Check" Site Funded By Biased Political Group,” Free Republic, Aug. 28, 2012.
- [8] E. Ravenscraft, “B.S. Detector Lets You Know When You're Reading a Fake News Source,” lifehacker. [Online]. Available: <https://lifehacker.com/b-s-detector-lets-you-know-when-youre-reading-a-fake-n-1789084038>. [Last Accessed: Dec. 03, 2017].
- [9] “The Webby Awards- Honoring the best of the internet” [Online]. Available: <https://www.webbyawards.com> . [Last Accessed: Dec. 03, 2017].
- [10] CalSwiss, “Fact Checking Websites: Pros and Cons,” The Daily Kos, 2016. [Online]. Available: <https://www.dailykos.com/stories/2016/12/1/1606289/-Fact-Checking-Websites-Pros-and-Cons>. [Last Accessed: Dec. 03, 2017].
- [11] M. J. Spivey, “Fake News and False Corroboration: Interactivity in Rumor Networks,” Proc. of the Annual Meeting of Cogn. Sci. Soc. 2017.

- [12] N. J. Conroy, V. L. Rubin, and Y. Chen, "Automatic deception detection: Methods for finding fake news," Proc. of the Assoc. for Info. Sci. and Technol. vol. 52, pp 1-4, 2015.
- [13] V. Narwal et al. "Automated Assistants to Identify and Prompt Action on Visual News Bias," arXiv preprint, arXiv: 1702.06492, 2017.
- [14] M. Farajtabar et al. "Fake News Mitigation via Point Process Based Intervention." arXiv preprint, arXiv: 1703.07823, 2017.
- [15] M. Conti et al. "It's Always April Fools' Day! On the Difficulty of Social Network Misinformation Classification via Propagation Features." arXiv preprint, arXiv:1701.04221, 2017.
- [16] S. Singhanian, F. Nigel, and S. Rao, "3HAN: A Deep Neural Network for Fake News Detection," International Conf. on Neural Info. Process. Springer, 2017.
- [17] N. Ruchansky, S. Seo, and Y. Liu, "CSI: A Hybrid Deep Model for Fake News Detection," Conf. on Info. and Knowl. Manag. 2017
- [18] J. Eembi, N. Che, I. Ishak, and F. Sidi, "Deception detection approach for data veracity in online digital news: Headlines vs contents," AIP Conf. Proc. vol. 1891, no. 1, AIP Publishing, 2017.
- [19] S. M. SIRAJUDEEN, N. F. A. AZMI, and A. I. ABUBAKAR, "Online Fake News Detection Algorithm," J. of Theoretical & Appl. Info. Technol. Vol 95, no. 17, 2017.
- [20] "Introduction to Support Vector Machines," OpenCV documentation. [Online]. Available:https://docs.opencv.org/2.4/doc/tutorials/ml/introduction_to_svm/introduction_to_svm.html. [Last Accessed: Dec. 03, 2017].
- [21] "Stochastic gradient descent," scikit-learn: machine learning in python. [Online]. Available: <http://scikit-learn.org/stable/modules/sgd.html>. [Last Accessed: Dec. 03, 2017].
- [22] "Scikit-learn," A free software machine learning library for Python. Available: <http://scikit-learn.org>
- [23] "NumPy," A library for the Python programming language. Available: www.numpy.org
- [24] "Pandas," A software library written for the Python programming language. Available: <https://pandas.pydata.org>

- [25] G. McIntire, “fake_real_news_dataset.”
Available: https://github.com/GeorgeMcIntire/fake_real_news_dataset
- [26] “NLTK,” Natural Language Toolkit. Available: <https://www.nltk.org>
- [27] A. L. Maas et al. “Learning word vectors for sentiment analysis,” Proc. of the 49th Annual Meeting of the Assoc. for Computat. Linguistics: Human Language Techn. Vol. 1, Assoc. for Comput. Linguistics, 2011.
- [28] P. Kolari et al, “Detecting spam blogs: A machine learning approach,” Assoc. for the Advancement of Artificial Intell. vol. 6, pp 1351-1356, 2006.
- [29] Jeff Schneider, “Cross Validation” [Online].
Available: <https://www.cs.cmu.edu/~schneide/tut5/node42.html>. [Last Accessed: Dec. 03, 2017].
- [30] R. Kohavi, “A study of cross-validation and bootstrap for accuracy estimation and model selection,” International Joint Conference on Artificial Intelligence, vol. 14, no. 2, 1995.
- [31] Y. LeCun, Y. Bengio, and G. Hinton, “Deep learning,” Nature, vol. 521, no. 7553, pp 436-444, 2015.